

PROPOSAL FOR AN UPDATED ARTS TEACHING: EMPHASIS ON CROSS-CUTTING THEMES AND PROJECTS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511682

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the theme 'proposal for an updated teaching of arts: emphasis on cross-cutting themes and projects.' Its scientific relevance lies in the aspect that it will contribute to raising the level of technical-intellectual knowledge with a view to application in Arts teaching. Its social relevance is that it can contribute to a greater understanding and dissemination of the concepts of arts and their epistemological nuances and social implications. By making and knowing art, students follow learning paths that provide specific knowledge about their relationship with the world, developing potentialities such as perception, observation, imagination and sensitivity that can underpin the awareness of their place in the world and that also undeniably contribute to their significant apprehension of the contents of the other

disciplines of the curriculum. It was the objective of this work to analyze that, through living with the universe of art, students can get to know artistic making as a poetic experience; as development of potentialities: perception, reflection, sensitivity, imagination, intuition, curiosity and flexibility; as interaction experience; as form; as cultural production. Artistic learning involves, therefore, a set of different types of knowledge, which aim to create meanings, fundamentally exercising the constant possibility of transformation of the human being. Understanding art as a production of meanings that are transformed in time and space allows us to contextualize the era in which we live in its relationships with others. A bibliographic research was carried out, based on consultations with books, magazines, newspapers and articles on the subject.

Keywords: artistic learning; cross-cutting themes; projects.

INTRODUCTION

The central issue of art teaching in Brazil concerns a huge gap between theoretical production, which has a path of constant questions and formulations, and teachers' access to this production, which is hampered by the fragility of their training, the small number of books published on the subject, not to mention the countless preconceived views that reduce artistic activity at school to a surface veneer, restricted to celebrating civic dates and decorating everyday school life.

In many schools, for example, mimeographed drawings with stereotypical shapes are still used for children to color or *songs are played* indicating actions for the school routine (snack time, dismissal time). In other words, we only work with self-expression; or, teachers are eager to teach art history and take students to museums, theaters and musical or dance performances. There are many other possibilities in which the versatile teacher invents original ways of working, armed only with his own initiative and self-taught research. This plurality of individual actions represents isolated experiences that have little opportunity for exchange, which takes place at events, regional congresses, where more and more teachers gather, but to which the vast majority do not have access.

This theme was chosen because the production and appreciation of art involves the ability to relate and resolve issues proposed by the organization of the elements that make up artistic forms: knowing art involves the joint exercise of thought, intuition, sensitivity and imagination.

CONCEPT ARTS

Art is human activity linked to manifestations of an aesthetic order, made by artists based on perceptions, emotions and ideas, with the aim of stimulating a conscious interest in one or more spectators, and each work of art has a meaning.

Without a clear awareness of their function and without a consistent foundation of art as an area of knowledge with specific content, teachers are unable to formulate a framework of conceptual and methodological references to support their pedagogical action; There is no adequate material for practical classes, nor quality teaching material to support theoretical classes.

Based on these findings, we sought to formulate principles that guide teachers in their reflection on the nature of artistic knowledge and in delimiting the space that the area of Art can occupy in elementary education, based on an investigation of the artistic phenomenon and how to teach and how to learn art.

According to Bronowski (2006), the universe of art characterizes a particular type of knowledge that human beings produce based on fundamental questions that they have always asked regarding their place in the world.

Artistic manifestation has in common with scientific, technical or philosophical knowledge its character of creation and innovation. Essentially, the creative act, in any of these forms of knowledge, structures and organizes the world, responding to the challenges that emanate from it, in a constant process of transformation of man and the surrounding reality. The product of creative action, innovation, results from the addition of new structural elements or the modification of others. Governed by the basic need for order, the human spirit continually creates its awareness of existence through diverse manifestations (BRONOWSKI, 2006, p. 36).

Human beings have always organized and classified natural phenomena, the cycle of seasons, the stars in the sky, the different plants and animals, social, political and economic relations, to understand their place in the universe, seeking the meaning of life.

According to Bastide (2003), both science and art respond to this need through the construction of objects of knowledge that, together with social, political and economic relations, philosophical and ethical systems, form the set of symbolic manifestations of a certain culture. Science and art are, therefore, products that express the imaginary representations of different cultures, which are renewed through time, building the course of human history.

The very idea of science as an autonomous discipline, distinct from art, is a recent product of Western culture. In ancient traditional societies there was no such distinction: art

integrated the life of human groups, permeated in rites, ceremonies and objects of daily use; Science was practiced by healers and priests, forming part of a mythical way of understanding reality.

Even in modern culture, the relationship between art and science presents itself in different ways, from the beginning of the Western world to the present day.

In the centuries following the Renaissance, art and science were increasingly considered as totally different areas of knowledge, generating a fallacious conception, according to which science was the product of rational thought and art, pure sensitivity.

In fact, it has never been possible to exist science without imagination, nor art without knowledge. Both are creative actions in the construction of human becoming. The very concept of scientific truth creates mobility, becomes provisional truth, which structurally brings the products of science and art closer together.

The dynamisms of the man who grasps reality in a poetic way and those of the man who thinks about it scientifically are peculiar and irreducible ways of accessing knowledge, but, at the same time, they are two aspects of psychic unity.

There is an increasingly accentuated tendency in contemporary investigations towards dimensioning the complementarity between art and science, clarifying the distinction between them and, at the same time, integrating them into a new understanding of the human being. New, but not that much. There are many works on the phenomenon of creativity that cite examples of people who wrote about the creative process itself (BRONOWSKI, 2006, p. 37).

Artists and scientists report similar occurrences, making it possible to systematize certain invariants, such as, for example, the culmination of the creative action, the famous “Eureka!”: the sudden moment of “I found it!” can occur to the mathematician when suddenly solving a problem, at a time when he is not thinking about the subject.

In the same way, a musician was walking after lunch, when an entire symphony came into his head; he just had to sit down afterwards to write it. It is clear that in both cases, both the mathematician and the musician spent a long time prior to maturing questions, based on a continuous process of data collection, investigating possibilities.

According to Bosi (2005), in general, this character of *sudden enlightenment* is common to art and science, as something that reveals itself to the creator's consciousness, coming to the surface independently of his will, whether at that moment or another, but being subsequent to an essential period of hard work on the subject.

For a scientist, a formula can be *beautiful* ; For a visual artist, the relationships between light and shapes are *problems to be resolved plastically* . It seems that there are much more things in common between these two forms of knowledge than our vain philosophy supposes.

This discussion is of particular interest to the field of education, which manifests an urgent need to formulate new paradigms that avoid the opposition between art and science, to face the political, social and techno-scientific transformations that herald the human being of the 21st century.

Only creative teaching, which favors the integration between students' rational and aesthetic learning, can contribute to the complementary joint exercise of reason and dream, in which knowing is also marveling, having fun, playing with the unknown, taking risks bold hypotheses, work hard, strive and rejoice in discoveries.

Each work of art is, at the same time, a cultural product of a specific era and a singular creation of the human imagination, whose value is universal. Therefore, a work of art is not more advanced, more evolved, nor more correct than any other.

Artistic knowledge does not aim to understand and define general laws that explain why things are the way they are. It takes place in singular, untranslatable moments, of the artist or the spectator with that particular work, in a particular instant. In the same way, artistic forms present a subjective synthesis of meanings constructed through poetic images (visual, sound, body, or sets of words, as in literary or theatrical texts). It is not a linear discourse about objects, facts, questions, ideas and feelings, it is rather a combination of images that are objects, facts, questions, ideas and feelings, ordered not by the laws of objective logic, but by a logic intrinsic to the domain of the imaginary. Therefore, art does not represent or reflect reality, it is reality perceived from another point of view.

The artist challenges things as they are, to reveal how they could be, according to a certain way of meaning the world that is his own. What essentially distinguishes artistic creation from other modalities of human knowledge is the quality of communication between human beings that the work of art provides, through a particular use of forms of language .

The embodiment of the artist's ideas and feelings in a form that can be grasped by the senses characterizes the artistic work as a product of human creation, considering that the product created by the artist provides a type of communication in which countless forms of meanings are condensed through the combination of certain elements, different for each artistic modality, such as: lines, shapes, colors and textures, in plastic form; pitch, timbre, intensity and

rhythm, in musical form; characters, space, text and setting, in theatrical form; and movement, design in space, rhythm and composition, in the form of dance.

Peixoto (2007) asks: What would this particular use of language forms be? In a journalistic text, the article may report on an end-of-year theater play that took place at school X, performed by a group of students, describing and reporting the event. Its objective is to inform the reader about the fact.

In the short story *Pirlimpisquice*, Guimarães Rosa (1908-1967) also talks about a similar event, in a completely different way. It is a poetic text that begins with the following phrase: “That in our little theater was Oh!”. In this sentence, the text does not just give information to the reader, but embodies a multiplicity of meanings related to the experience of a group of students who performed an end-of-year play at a priests' college.

The expression “it was from Oh!” is a poetic synthesis that makes sense for the reader within the text as a whole and contains everything that is reported below, at the same time that allows him to give this “Oh!” their own meanings. What does this expression mean? Amazement, wonder, rapture, fright, fear and many other things for each reader.

What matters is that, instead of describing in detail what the experience was, Guimarães Rosa condenses this entire experience into a single synthetic sentence which, as a poetic image, is a particular way of using the possibilities of language, creating a different type of communication. between people.

Just as each sentence gains meaning within the text as a whole, creating the whole of the literary form, each visual, musical, dramatic or movement element has its place and relates to the others in that specific artistic form. The artistic form speaks for itself, is independent of and goes beyond the artist's intentions.

Guernica, a painting painted by Pablo Picasso (1881-1973), contains the idea of the author's repudiation of the horrors of war. An individual who is unaware of Picasso's conscious intentions can view *Guernica* and feel a significant impact; meaning is the product revealed when the conflicting relationship between the images of the work and the data of personal experience occurs.

The artistic form can mean different things, resulting from each person's experience of appreciation. Whether in the form of allegory, critical formulation, discovery of formal patterns, ideological propaganda, or pure poetry, the work of art gains meaning in the enjoyment of each spectator. Aesthetic perception is the key to artistic communication. IN THE process of

knowledge, of which aesthetic appreciation is a part, the privileged channel of understanding is the quality of the sensitive experience of perception.

When faced with a work of art, skills of perception, intuition, reasoning and imagination act on both the artist and the spectator, but it is initially through the channel of sensitivity that contact is established between the artist and the spectator, mediated by aesthetic perception. of the work of art. The process of knowledge comes from meaningful relationships, from the perception of the qualities of lines, textures, colors, sounds, movements , *etc.* (BOSI, 2005, p. 56)

When Guimarães Rosa wrote: *Clouds, lint of coconut ice cream* “he created an artistic form in which metaphor, a special way of using language, brought together elements that, in reality, were separate, but came together in a poetic phrase through the creative action of artist” (BRASIL, 1998, p. 109).

In this aesthetic appreciation, not only the exercise of intellective ability is important; but, mainly, that the reader is able to let themselves be touched sensitively to be able to perceive, for example, the qualities of weight, light, texture, density and color contained in the images of clouds and strands of coconut ice cream; at the same time, the experience that this person has or does not have of observing clouds, of liking or not liking coconut ice cream, of knowing or not what a metaphor is, make the images of the text resonate in their own internal images and allow them to create the particular meaning that the text reveals to you.

Meaning is not, therefore, in the work, but in the complex interaction of a primarily imaginative nature between the work and the viewer. The artist's personality is an ingredient that becomes a creative gesture, forming part of the very substance of the work . The data of sensitivity become expressive matter in such a way that they configure the very content of the work of art: what is perceived through the senses becomes a construction made of formal relationships through artistic creation.

The engine that organizes this set is sensitivity: emotion (from the Latin *emovere* meaning 'what moves') triggers the artist's creative dynamism. This condition of emotion that causes the impact on the appreciator resonates, within him, the movement that triggers new significant combinations between his internal images in contact with the images of the work of art, but the work of art is not the result only of the sensitivity of the artist, just as the spectator's aesthetic emotion does not come solely from the feeling that the work evokes in him.

Creative imagination allows human beings to conceive situations, facts, ideas and feelings that are realized as internal images, through the manipulation of language. It is this ability to form images that makes the evolution of man and the development of the child

possible; Visualizing situations that do not exist, but that may come to exist, opens access to possibilities that are beyond immediate experience.

Emotion is movement, imagination gives shape and density to the experience of perceiving, feeling and thinking, creating internal images that combine to represent this experience. The imaginative faculty is at the root of any knowledge process, whether scientific, artistic or technical.

It is important that students understand the meaning of artistic creation; that their experiences of drawing, singing, dancing or dramatizing are not activities designed to distract them from the *seriousness* of other subjects.

ARTS TEACHING AS A WAY OF PROVIDING STUDENTS WITH KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THEMSELVES AND THE WORLD

According to Read (2007), making art and thinking about the artistic work that is carried out, as well as about the art that is and was realized in history, can guarantee the student a learning situation connected with the values and modes of artistic production. in sociocultural environments.

According to Argan (2007), learning art is progressively developing a path of cultivated personal creation, that is, fed by the meaningful interactions that the student carries out with those who bring relevant information to the learning process (other students, teachers, artists, specialists) , with sources of information (works, colleagues' work, collections, reproductions, exhibitions, presentations) and with his own journey as a creator.

Teaching art in line with the student's learning modes means, then, not isolating the school from information about the historical and social production of art and, at the same time, guaranteeing the student the freedom to imagine and build personal or group artistic proposals. based on own intentions. And all of this is integrated with the playful and pleasurable aspects that appear during the artistic activity. Thus, learning with meaning and pleasure is associated with a clearer understanding of what is taught. To this end, the contents of art cannot be trivialized, but must be taught through situations and/or proposals that reach the student's ways of learning and guarantee the participation of each person within the classroom. Such guidelines favor the emergence of personal formulations of ideas, hypotheses, theories and artistic forms. Progressively and through continuous work, these formulations tend to move closer to more elaborate ways of doing and thinking about art. Introducing primary school students to the origins of theater or drama texts through narrated stories can arouse greater interest and curiosity without losing the integrity of the content and historical facts (ARGAN, 2007, p. 38).

It is up to the teacher to choose the appropriate teaching methods and resources to present information, always observing the need to introduce artistic forms because teaching art with art is the most effective way.

In other words, the literary text, the song and the image will bring more knowledge to the student and will be more effective as carriers of information and meaning.

The student, in learning situations, needs to be invited to practice the practices of learning to see, observe, hear, act, touch and reflect on them. Therefore, the teacher will introduce means into the student's daily life so that these practices can take place, enabling a better way of taking these works into the children's world or taking children to them.

It is the school's role to include information about art produced at regional, national and international levels, also critically understanding that produced by the media to democratize knowledge and expand the student's possibilities for social participation. It is noteworthy that the student's creative path, covering expressive and constructive aspects, is the central focus of the school's guidance and planning. Elementary school is a special school moment in students' lives, because it is at this point in their development that they tend to get closer to issues in the adult world and try to understand them within their possibilities. They are curious about topics such as the dynamics of social relations, work relations, how and by whom things are produced (BARBOSA, 2004, p. 27).

If student learning was based on experience, everything stated by the author would be a direct consequence of the teaching process. But, in the mechanism of mass education, this condition is lost and there is no way to even achieve the theoretical objectives presented in the curriculum, because the teacher himself is lost in his increasingly bureaucratic tasks assigned to him by the system.

Teaching art is an [*almost*] impossible task. Learning art is completely impossible, because it is an expression of a feeling and a perception about an object with which there is direct contact, through the senses and the result is an idealized projection, a product of the poetic license that accompanies the artist since forever.

What common sense takes as talent refers to the freedom to expose your vision processes about the world and its representations without this disturbing your interpretation of reality. How to take this unique condition into a formal educational environment, with its strict rules and pre-defined models, is the great challenge faced by teachers and didactics, especially because when the results are different from what was recommended, all kinds of excuses and accusations are made. , without anyone saying how inappropriate and inappropriate the environment designed for art classes is. In the same place that Mathematics and Portuguese are taught, the aim is to teach Literature, Science and Art; in other words, it is trying to place

completely different components at the same level of abstraction that present didactic requirements that are equally *sui generis* .

With regard to art, specifically, the student can become aware of the existence of a concrete social production and observe that this production has history. Read argues that,

The student can also observe that artistic works involve the acquisition of codes and skills that they want to master to incorporate into their work. This desire for mastery is correlated to the new perception that one can assimilate artistic forms created by people or social groups, by following a path of personal artistic work. This procedure reduces the gap between what the student projects and what they want to achieve. Therefore, it is at the end of this period that the student, developing representation practices through a process of continuous dedication, will master codes socially constructed in art, without losing their way of articulating such information or their originality. (READ, 2007, p. 19)

Learning in art accompanies the general development process of children and young people during this period, who observe that their participation in everyday social activities are involved in the regularities, agreements, constructions and laws that they recognize in the social dynamics of the community to which they belong, at least fact of perceiving itself as a constitutive part of this.

It is also up to the school to guide its work with the objective of preserving and boosting the dynamics of development and learning, preserving student autonomy and encouraging systematic contact with the contents, themes and activities that will best guarantee their progress and integration as a student. This set of considerations about ways of learning and teaching art makes it possible to review theories about the art of children and adolescents.

Artistic action also usually involves group creation: at this point, art contributes to strengthening the concept of a group as a socializer and creator of an imaginary universe, updating references and developing its own history. Art makes the group present to itself, through its imaginary representations. The playful aspect of this activity is fundamental.

When playing, the child develops rhythmic and melodic activities, dresses up as an adult, produces drawings, dances, and invents stories. But this place of playful activity in early childhood is increasingly replaced, outside and inside school, by situations that previously favor the mechanical reproduction of values imposed by mass culture to the detriment of imaginative experience.

Although young people always have a great interest in learning how to make shapes present in their surroundings, they continue to develop their individual creative path, which cannot be lost. The student can and wants to create their own images based on a particular

personal experience, something they have lived or learned, the choice of a theme, a technique, or an influence, or a contact with nature and so on.

It is also up to the teacher both to feed students with information and art procedures that they can and want to master and to know how to guide and preserve the development of personal work, providing the student with the opportunity to make their own choices to implement personal and group projects.

The quality of the pedagogical action that considers both the skills related to aesthetic perception and those involved in artistic creation can contribute to strengthening the student's creative awareness, leading them to create their own works.

The student becomes demanding and very critical in relation to his own production, precisely because at this point in his development he can now compare it, in a more systematic way, to those of the circle of social production to which he has access. This characterization of the student has led to the belief that during this period the child is less spontaneous and less creative in artistic activities than in the period before schooling.

Students in the first to fourth grades of elementary school seek to get closer to the cultural production of art. However, such interests cannot be confused with submission to adult standards of art. The full experience of this moment will allow young people to structure their own works, with an individual mark, inaugurating autonomous poetic propositions that assimilate influences and transform the work they develop within their creative path in the various forms of art. In the subsequent period, from the fifth to the eighth grades, this experience will allow us to create our own poetics, implemented with intentionality.

The area must be incorporated with broad objectives that meet the characteristics of learning, combining artistic practice with knowledge and reflection on art. These objectives must ensure student learning on the perceptual, imaginative and productive planes.

Regarding content, the teaching of the area is oriented towards embracing the diversity of the cultural repertoire that the child brings to school, working with products from the community in which the school is located and also introducing production information social based on selection criteria appropriate to the student's participation in society as an informed citizen.

Training in art, which includes knowledge of what is and has been produced in different communities, should encourage the appreciation of people through the recognition of similarities and contrasts, qualities and specificities, which can open up the range of multiple

choices that young people will have to accomplish throughout its growth, in consolidating its identity.

The artistic phenomenon is present in different manifestations that make up the collections of popular and erudite culture, modern media and new technologies. Furthermore, art does not always present itself in everyday life as a work of art. But it can be observed in the shape of objects, in the arrangement of shop windows, in the music played by net pullers, in the litanies sung by traditional tapestry makers, in the street dance performed by boys and girls, in sales pitches, in gardens, in clothing, etc. . Encouraging curiosity about the artistic manifestation of different cultures, their beliefs, uses and customs, can awaken students' interest in values different from their own, promoting respect and recognition of these distinctions; This highlights the intrinsic relevance of each group and its set of values, enabling students to recognize in themselves and value in others the artistic ability to express themselves in diversity. Art teaching is an area of knowledge with specific content and must be consolidated as a constituent part of school curricula, therefore requiring teacher training to guide student training (FERRAZ and FUSARI, 2007, p. 53).

The set of contents is articulated within the context of teaching and learning along three guiding axes: production, enjoyment and reflection . Production refers to artistic making and the set of issues related to it, within the scope of the student's and social art producers' work.

Enjoyment refers to the meaningful appreciation of art and the universe related to it. This action contemplates the enjoyment of students' production and historical-social production in its diversity.

Reflection refers to the construction of knowledge about personal and colleagues' artistic work and about art as a product of history and the multiplicity of human cultures, with an emphasis on the cultivated formation of citizens. The three axes are articulated in practice, while maintaining their own spaces.

Thus, the contents can be worked on in any order, according to the teacher's decision, in accordance with the team's curricular design:

It is known that, in schools and the communities where they are located, there is a diversity of human and material resources available; therefore, considering the concrete reality of schools, some fundamental aspects for the projects to be developed stand out. It is desirable that students, throughout their schooling, have the opportunity to experience as many forms of art as possible; however, this needs to occur so that each artistic modality can be developed and deepened. Based on these premises, the contents of the Art area must be related in such a way that they can consolidate the artistic learning of elementary school students. Such learning concerns the possibility for students to develop a continuous and increasingly complex process in the domain of artistic and aesthetic knowledge, whether in the exercise of their own creative process, through artistic forms, or in contact with works of art and other forms present in cultures or in nature. The study, analysis and

appreciation of forms can contribute both to the students' personal process of creation and also to the progressive and significant knowledge of the role that art plays in human cultures (PEIXOTO , 2007, p. 59).

Every culture has its expression of art, which is the way of exposing your thoughts and knowledge about things you do not understand. From body paintings to great palaces and cathedrals, sculptures, pyramids, each of these works demonstrates what is kept in the memory of people in terms of beliefs, achievements and defeats. Painting and sculpture are the great revolutions and, sometimes, they are more exalted, due to the fact that they require little refinement from the individual, as long as they have good vision conditions and aesthetics is a natural condition of the human being, in which this is understands harmony in the composition of colors and elements represented.

Education in the field of art should be to teach how to refine aesthetic taste; but, contrary to this, what has been intended is to encourage attraction to the bizarre and the nonconformity of the elements in the landscape structure. The vision of a natural landscape demonstrates its beauty, because, in some way, there was an organizer of all the chaos that is represented. Contrary to this, when man interferes in the transformation of space, he is required to create a perfect space without distortions; in other words, the representation of the Dionysian is not accepted as something of aesthetic value to be appreciated, since it characterizes unresolved conflicts within the artist's thought.

In the field of art and, with the intention of making it something linked to formal didactic processes, visual arts were produced and thought of as a human element that can bring together various artistic forms, surpassing the procedures and interpretation of art, in its own way. classics.

VISUAL ARTS

The visual arts, in addition to traditional forms (painting, sculpture, drawing, engraving, architecture, artifact, industrial design), include other modalities that result from technological advances and aesthetic transformations since modernity (photography, graphic arts, cinema, television, video, computing, performance).

Each of these visualities is used in a particular way and in various possibilities of combinations between images, through which students can express themselves and communicate with each other in different ways.

The current world is characterized by the use of visuality in quantities unparalleled in history, creating a universe of multiple exposure for human beings, which generates the need for education to know how to perceive and distinguish feelings, sensations, ideas and qualities. Therefore, the study of visualities can be integrated into educational projects. Such learning can promote broader understandings so that the student can develop their sensitivity, affectivity and concepts and position themselves critically.

Visual arts education requires continually informed work on content and experiences related to materials, techniques and visual forms from different moments in history, including contemporary ones. To this end, the school must collaborate so that students go through a broad set of learning and creating experiences, articulating perception, imagination, sensitivity, knowledge and personal and group artistic production.

Visual education must consider the complexity of an educational proposal that takes into account the possibilities and ways for students to transform their knowledge into art, that is, the way they learn, create and develop in the area, creating and perceiving visual forms implies frequently work with the relationships between the elements that compose them, such as point, line, plane, color, light, movement and rhythm.

The articulations of these elements in the images give rise to the configuration of codes that transform over time. Such image formation standards can be assimilated by students as knowledge and recreating and updated practical application in their work, as their projects demand and their sensitivity and conditions to achieve them allow. The student also creates his poetics where he generates personal codes.

Furthermore, it is necessary to consider the techniques, procedures, historical information, producers, cultural and social relationships involved in the experience that will support your representations (concepts or theories) about art. Such representations transform throughout development as the learning process progresses.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Learning arts is a complex situation that defies academic logic, because to learn effectively, there is a need for direct empirical contact with objects and situations, that is, it is experience that determines the absorption potential and acquisition of knowledge, not theory through oral exposition.

Therefore, a learning proposal would be through didactic projects, in which the methodology applied would bring students closer to the reality of an artist, that is, their freedom

to express their feelings about the objects that cross them, hence the inclusion of transversal themes, as a way of promoting the expansion of students' creative potential.

The mismatches between the idea of offering art classes in basic education and the effective teaching of the technique, in itself, means that the entire pedagogical proposal for the component ends up as a utopia impossible for the school to overcome and its condition conflicting with the guarantees of promotion of constitutional rights. Art requires an effort and a challenge that goes beyond the egoic satisfaction of the State and all its proselytism of producing a citizen with broad thinking and a creative capacity in all areas of knowledge.

Unless the State reinvents its ways of thinking and producing knowledge, providing empirical learning mechanisms, art teaching will continue to be a moment of distraction for students and a mere extra content in the curricular proposal. There is no way to discover a potential artist without the individual being able to express what is concrete in their intellectual world. Learning workshops would be an excellent alternative to discover and develop talents in various artistic fields, based on practical classes in well-established studios coordinated by professionals who have mastered the techniques in question.

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